

SOME ISSUES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NON-OIL SECTOR IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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***Abstract.** The process of globalization expanded rapidly from the end of the 20th century to the beginning of the 21st century, and it can be said that it has achieved its faster pace of development against the background of the formation of economic dependence and close economic interaction between countries. The process of globalization also creates unique new challenges and destructive tendencies. As a rule, the main economic advantages of the globalization process are obtained by developed countries, or rather, by producers and inventors of industrial products, including capital and science-intensive products on the world market. The dominance of raw materials in the structure of production and export of developing countries essentially determines the dependence of developing countries on economically developed countries. The point is that developing countries are exporting more raw materials, including oil and gas resources, to the world market. The export of oil and gas resources also causes unique shocks and crises in the world market, and in most cases, these crises are relatively distant from economic processes and play the role of military and political threats. Taking into account all this, developed countries are trying to achieve ecological balance under the name of green energy transition, as well as getting rid of the economic dependence of oil exporting countries as their biggest goal. In recent years, especially in the countries that have joined the*

European Union, including Germany, and in addition, in Japan, trends such as reduction of oil and gas consumption have been observed in the structure of energy consumption. In general, the countries of the European Union prefer green energy, including the use of renewable energy sources, in order to reduce dependence on oil. Therefore, this trend brings unique changes to the development of the Republic of Azerbaijan, one of the oil exporting countries in the post-oil era.

Keywords: *Republic of Azerbaijan, green energy, non-oil sector, renewable energy sources, agriculture, tourism, economic stability, comparative advantages, gas emission, economic efficiency, gross domestic product.*

Statement of the problem. The process of making necessary changes in the state's economic strategy has already become the requirements of the modern era, taking into account the modern challenges of the globalization process in the Republic of Azerbaijan, which is living its 32nd year of independence. The most important vector of these requirements is that the main part of the country's economy and state budget revenues are almost formed due to revenues from the oil sector. In the future period, more precisely, in the post-oil era, the acceleration of the socio-economic development of the country requires, first of all, the development of the non-oil sector. The development of the non-oil sector means, first of all, the income from the state budget to the oil account in the economy of oil-dependent countries is compensated by the income from the export of products produced in the non-oil sector. The development of the non-oil sector is, in fact, important in terms of preventing the Dutch syndrome in the economy. One of the most creative ways to develop the non-oil sector should be to diversify the economy. Diversification of the economy, first of all, consists in ensuring the increase of export revenues from various sources to the state budget by achieving the development of parallel fields in the structure of exports. At this time, it is also necessary to take into account that, due to diversification, it is necessary to achieve the provision of income from different areas, which should be aimed at preventing dependence on one area and neutralizing

the dependence of inputs from one area on the market connector. Taking into account all this, it can be concluded that in the post-oil era, the development of the non-oil sector should be achieved within the framework of the necessary measures to accelerate the socio-economic development of the Republic of Azerbaijan. It is impossible to accelerate the development of the country's economy in the future without achieving the development of the non-oil sector. Thus, the development of the non-oil sector, in fact, is becoming more relevant against the background of modern challenges of globalization.

It is necessary to admit that there are quite wide potential opportunities in terms of developing the non-oil sector in the Republic of Azerbaijan. In order to achieve the development of the non-oil sector in the current conditions, increasing the competitiveness of the products produced in the mentioned areas, as well as increasing the quality of the products, should be considered as one of the important conditions. As is known, the deepening globalization trends are characterized by the emergence of more global economic and financial crises. In addition, the serial nature of economic crises causes severe fluctuations in the international market as well as global markets. This process causes destructive trends in the economy of countries that depend only on the import of one product. Therefore, in order to develop the non-oil sector in the post-oil era in the Republic of Azerbaijan and increase the amount of income from this area to the state budget, a reliable foundation should be created, which should essentially lead to an increase in the amount of added value created in the economy and an increase in the number of jobs.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. The objective necessity of the development of the non-oil sector is determined, first of all, by the elimination of the Dutch disease, which may arise against the background of the increase in the volume of oil imports in oil-producing countries, as well as the implementation of necessary measures in the direction of economic diversification. In general, the development of the non-oil sector reflects a set of measures aimed at eliminating dependence on oil, and quite a number of scientific ideas can be found in world scientific publications in

this direction. Many oil-rich countries have not been able to direct their oil revenues to improve the standard of living of their citizens. Of the 48 countries where oil exports accounted for more than 30% of total exports between 1965 and 1995, almost half were ranked at the bottom of the 2002 UN human development report. The report ranks countries according to poverty, education, health and other indicators of quality of life. Only 1/4 of these countries occupy the top 3/1 of the list, and many of them, such as Norway and Canada, achieved this before oil exports became a major source of income. Oxfam's study shows that oil and other mineral resources not only do not reduce poverty, but actually increase it [10]. In fact, it is possible to agree with the author's opinion that, especially when approaching the problem from the point of view of the increase in the level of poverty in African countries, it is indeed possible to conclude that oil and other mineral resources do not really reduce poverty. At the same time, the more the income obtained from the export of oil and other natural resources takes a dominant position in the country's economy, the more it can prevent food shortages and the development of other areas, and actually increases the level of poverty.

The destructive tendencies that can arise in the background of the emergence of the economy's dependence on oil have manifested themselves more sharply, especially in the background of the increase in the level of inflation. In this regard, the term Dutch disease, which has maintained its popularity in the modern realities of the world economy, has not lost its relevance today. The term Dutch disease was introduced in 1977 by The Economist magazine. The effect got its name from the Groningen gas field, which was discovered in 1959 in the north of the Netherlands. The rapid growth of gas exports due to field development in the 70s of the last century led to an increase in inflation and unemployment, and a decrease in the growth rates of exports and incomes of manufactured products. The rise in oil prices in the mid-70s and early 80s of the last century led to similar manifestations in Saudi Arabia, Nigeria, and Mexico [19]. When oil prices are high, governments spend heavily and hardly justify their savings for crisis situations. Often, the government

also embarks on ambitious long-term and capital-intensive projects to capitalize on incoming revenues. But budgets designed for a certain level of oil prices have to be cut if the price changes significantly. At this time, in fact, drastic budget changes are very harmful. Governments often have to borrow to finance their obligations during oil booms. When the price of oil is low, the government has to borrow on unfavorable terms, which leads to the accumulation of a lot of debt on those countries [13]. According to Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor Rufat Guliyev, the process of increasing the volume of income from oil is cyclical in some cases and depends more on economic crises and especially oil crises. Per capita income in Saudi Arabia decreased from 28,600 US dollars in 1981 to 6,800 US dollars in 2001. Equator's foreign debt was equal to 217 million US dollars in 1972, when oil was discovered there, and in 2002, this indicator rose to 11.8 billion US dollars. In Angola, as noted by the International Monetary Fund, more than one billion oil money almost "disappears" every year. In general, the abundance of natural resources in some cases makes it difficult to transition to a market economy and stimulate the development of free enterprise. One of the main reasons for this is that the economy's reaction to reforms is quite slow. Another reason is that the government has overly optimistic hopes for future oil revenues [12, p. 382]. In general, the optimistic forecasts of the governments of the oil-exporting countries regarding the income from oil, in a number of cases, in particular, in the framework of large-scale borrowing against the background of sharp financial crises and falling oil prices, almost end on pessimistic notes. This causes destructive trends in the social, political and economic life of countries that do not diversify their economy.

In addition to agreeing with certain points in Professor Rufat Guliyev's opinion, we would also like to add that Saudi Arabia and Norway, among the world's oil exporting countries, have taken necessary measures to diversify the economy, which conditions the efficient use of oil revenues. In fact, quite positive trends towards the development of the non-oil sector are evident in the mentioned countries.

It is true that it is necessary to admit that in the 70s and 80s of the last century, the attempt to reform agriculture in the direction of developing the non-oil sector in Saudi Arabia failed in one way or another. For example, in the 70s of the last century, the government of Saudi Arabia began to implement the necessary measures towards the implementation of the import substitution program. Under the name of the state grain policy, the Saudi Arabian economy was planned to be completely free from imports under the development program. To achieve the goals, first of all, state subsidies and import-limiting customs tariffs were introduced. To achieve the goals, first of all, state subsidies and import-limiting customs tariffs were introduced. The government provided a certain amount of subsidies to agribusinesses for manure, seeds, irrigation, machinery and wages. In addition, farmers began to buy grain 3 times more expensive than the world price. As a result, production increased 26 times, from 200,000 tons in 1980 to 4 million tons in 1992. More than 500,000 tons of net import in the 80s of the last century turned into 2 million tons of net export in 1992. In general, it is no coincidence that in the early 90s of the last century, Saudi Arabia became the 6th largest exporter of wheat in the world [14, p. 239-246].

In our opinion, the most important factor that caused the development of the non-oil sector in Saudi Arabia to be ineffective was the dominant position of religious politics in the country. So, in fact, the development of the non-oil sector, especially in agriculture, which is one of its most important sectors, had to be subordinated to the interests of agrarian business, that is, commercial processes. However, the policy implemented in the country, in fact, prioritized generous food aid to African countries in this area. All this, in fact, did not promise significant progress in the development of agriculture as an important component of the non-oil sector. However, the fact that the country was the 6th largest grain exporter in the world in the 90s can be characterized as vectors of positive progress in this field.

The conducted studies show that among the oil exporting countries, Norway can be considered the country that is relatively less dependent on oil. In fact, this is due to the fact that the mentioned country has significantly less dependence on the

hydrocarbon market compared to other oil-producing countries, and at the same time, it uses oil inputs effectively. Currently, in 2006, GDP per capita exceeded 60,000 US dollars, and about 20,000 dollars of this indicator is made up of the hydrocarbon market. In general, the GDP is significantly higher than that of Eastern European countries, but lower than that of neighboring Sweden, the Netherlands, and Central European countries [11, p. 165-166] .

It should be noted that the need to develop the non-oil sector in oil-producing and oil-exporting countries is also due to the fact that countries around the world give more preference to green energy. As we mentioned above, this process is explained by the preservation of the ecological balance, but in fact, it is aimed at neutralizing the dependence of developed industrial powers on the countries that export raw materials from time to time.

The concept of green economy was first introduced into the scientific circulation in 1989, focusing on a more harmonious reconciliation of economic and environmental issues [18, p. 192]. Despite the lack of a single point of view on the concept of green energy in the literature, or rather a single scientific approach, most experts justify it as the actualization of green energy use processes, the transition to the use of renewable energy sources, which are considered more sustainable than depleted mineral resources [15, p. 85].

As we mentioned above, the world energy market is actually quite sensitive to epidemics, crises, and military-political processes. For example, in 2020, an almost sharp decline was observed in the global oil products market. And this decrease was primarily closely related to the coronavirus pandemic. In 2021, due to the relaxation of the quarantine regime, an increase was observed in the world market of oil products. For example, in 2020, the volume of the world oil products market decreased by 9.2%, while in 2021, the world demand for oil products increased by 5%. In general, the largest consumer of oil products in the world in 2021 was the United States, which accounted for 17% of the world's consumption of products. However, despite all this, it should be noted that in European countries, especially in

Germany, a decrease in the demand for oil products was observed, which was caused by a 2.9% decrease. (Enerdata data on world energy and climate annual, 2022).

In general, during the last 30 years, a decrease in the intensity of energy used per unit of gross domestic product has been observed.

In Japan, after the "Oil shocks" of the 70s of the last century, the development of the policy of energy saving and reduction of the need for fossil fuels began to be observed. Thus, for the 70-90 years of the last century, the energy efficiency of the economy increased by 35% in Japan. And the mentioned country has achieved the highest energy efficiency index in the world in all industrial fields. However, in the period after the 90s of the last century, or rather, including 2010, environmental protection issues and global climate change problems are more evident in the energy conservation policy. Priority transfers in one way or another are observed in state policy. And this was primarily due to the preference of activities directed to the expansion of measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions[9, p. 19-20]. The intensity of energy consumption per unit of GDP is shown as follows:

As can be seen from the picture, energy intensity in the Japanese economy is one of the lowest in the world. In 2019, Japan's energy intensity index was 2.7 times lower than the corresponding index of Russia, 2.2 times lower than the corresponding index of the United States, and 1.6 times lower than the corresponding index of

China. Even in 2019, the indicator of the intensity of energy consumption per product unit in Japan was even lower compared to Germany. This allows us to conclude that energy efficiency in Japan is higher than in Germany.

Therefore, summarizing the above-mentioned, it can be concluded that such a trend is more evident in international publications that the transition to green energy is accompanied by a significant limitation of oil and gas consumption. And taking into account all this, there is a greater need to strengthen measures aimed at the development of the non-oil sector in oil-exporting countries, including in our republic. In general, in the near future, significant progress should be made in the field of development of the non-oil sector, which can essentially characterize the country's fundamental preparation for the post-oil era.

The purpose and tasks of the article. The purpose of the article is to prepare scientifically based and practical suggestions on accelerating the development of the non-oil sector in the Republic of Azerbaijan in the post-oil era. The duties of the article include:

- Analysis of adequate trends in the economy of oil-exporting countries as a result of connector fluctuations in the world oil market;
- Analysis of considerations related to the prevention of the destructive consequences of Holland's syndrome;
- Analysis of trends in the world energy resources market;
- Analysis of fluctuations in oil and gas consumption in the world in connection with the transition to green energy;
- Analysis of the current situation of the development of the non-oil sector of the Republic of Azerbaijan;
- Determining the priorities of the development of the non-oil sector in the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Main text. In modern conditions, where the process of globalization is deepening, ensuring the economic security of the Republic of Azerbaijan depends significantly on the development of the oil and gas sector. It should be taken into

account that the oil sector has played a decisive role in the economy of Azerbaijan since the former Soviet Union. After gaining independence, more precisely, in 1994, the signing of the century oil contracts in Azerbaijan was accompanied by large-scale investments in the oil sector of the economy. And the trends of rapid growth in the oil sector of the economy as a whole have also manifested themselves. Based on the data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, it can be concluded that the share of the mining industry in the industrial sector of the country's economy is 73.3% in 2018, 69.9% in 2019, 61.3% in 2021, and 61.3% in 2022. and it was 65.6% in the year. In the structure of the mining industry, the share of crude oil and natural gas production was 65.9% in 2018, 62.3% in 2019, 51.9% in 2021, and 61% in 2022[5, etc. 24]. In 2021, 34 million 580.3 tons of oil were produced in the Republic of Azerbaijan, which is 8.9% more than in 2018. Also, the volume of commercial oil production in the country was 34 million 513.3 tons in 2021, which is 8.9 times higher than in the comparable period. In 2021, 43 billion 867.3 million cubic meters of gas were produced in the Republic of Azerbaijan, which is 43.9% more than in 2018. The volume of commercial gas production in 2021 was 32 billion 578.3 million cubic meters, which is 69.6% more than in 2018 [5, p. 35-36].

Analyzing the structure of investments directed to fixed capital in the industry, it can be concluded that in the structure of investments as a whole, the volume of investments directed to the mining industry, including the oil-gas and natural gas production sector, is quite high. So, if in 2018 the volume of investments in the mining industry was 67.1% of the structure of total investments, in 2021 this indicator was equal to 64.2%. Investments in the crude oil and natural gas production sector accounted for 66.8% of investments in the mining industry as a whole in 2018, and 63% in 2021[5, p. 75]. From the analysis of statistical data, it can be concluded that in 2018-2021, a decrease in the volume of investments made in the mining industry, as well as in the crude oil and natural gas production sector is observed in one way or another.

It should be noted that since the beginning of the 2000s, a series of decrees and orders have been adopted by the country's president regarding the development of the oil sector of the economy. It should be taken into account that other regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan, with the exception of the Baku Agglomeration, almost have the potential to specialize in the development of the non-oil sector. By the order of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated March 30, 2006, Azerbaijan Investment Company was established for the purpose of promotion of investments in the development of non-oil sectors of the economy, renewal of the material and technological base of existing enterprises in these sectors. In addition, in order to support the development of business activities, the entrepreneurship council operates under the president.

It can be noted that "The decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated January 29, 2019 on the approval of the state program for the socio-economic development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2019-2023 is significant in the direction of the development of the non-oil sector and the attraction of foreign investments in this field." can be considered a state act. The presidential decree states that the development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan is an important component of the sustainable socio-economic development strategy successfully implemented in the country. The implementation of the tasks provided for in the adopted and successfully implemented state programs in the field of regional development, as well as in the orders on additional measures for the socio-economic development of the regions, will contribute to the sustainable development of the non-oil sector in the country, the improvement of the quality of communal services and social infrastructure provision in the regions, and the further improvement of the entrepreneurial environment. , has given impetus to the increase of investment, the opening of new enterprises, jobs and, as a result, to increase the employment of the population and reduce the level of poverty. During the years 2004-2018, when the state programs were implemented, the gross domestic product increased 3.3 times, including 2.8 times in the non-oil sector, 2.6 times in industry, and 1.7 times in

agriculture. As a result of targeted measures implemented during this period, 2 million new jobs, 1.5 million of them permanent, more than 100 thousand enterprises were created in the country, unemployment decreased to 5%, and poverty level decreased to 5.1% [1]. The volume and structure of gross domestic product production in the oil-gas and non-oil-gas sectors of the economy is reflected in the following table:

Table: Structure and dynamics of gross domestic product production in the oil-gas and non-oil-gas sectors of the economy

Gross domestic product production in the oil-gas and non-oil-gas sectors of the economy

Table: compiled based on the data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Azerbaijan national accounts, statistical collection, Baku, 2022, p. 19.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	
Ümumi daxili məhsul - cəmi cari qiymətlərlə, mlyn. manat	70 337,8	80 092,0	81 896,2	72 578,1	92 857,7	<i>Gross domestic product - total current prices, mln.manats</i>
						<i>as percentage of the pervious year</i>
əvvəlki ilə nisbətən, faizlə	100,2	101,5	102,5	95,8	105,6	year
o cümlədən:						<i>of which:</i>
neft-qaz sektoru						<i>oil-gas sector</i>
cari qiymətlərlə, mlyn. manat	25 005,4	32 231,7	30 051,9	20 417,5	33 930,6	<i>current prices, mln.manats</i>
						<i>as percentage of the pervious year</i>
əvvəlki ilə nisbətən, faizlə	94,7	100,5	100,4	93,5	101,2	year
qeyri neft-qaz sektoru						<i>non oil-gas sector</i>
cari qiymətlərlə, mlyn. manat	40 328,0	41 662,0	44 481,8	45 312,2	51 082,9	<i>current prices, mln.manats</i>
						<i>as percentage of the pervious year</i>
əvvəlki ilə nisbətən, faizlə	102,8	102,0	104,0	97,1	107,1	year
məhsula və idxala xalis vergilər						<i>net taxes on product and import</i>
cari qiymətlərlə, mlyn. manat	5 004,4	6 198,3	7 362,5	6 848,4	7 844,2	<i>current prices, mln.manats</i>
						<i>as percentage of the pervious year</i>
əvvəlki ilə nisbətən, faizlə	102,5	101,6	103,1	96,8	108,6	year

As can be seen from the table, in 2021, compared to 2017, the volume of gross domestic product in the Republic of Azerbaijan at current prices was 92,857.7 million manats, which is 32% more than in 2017. The volume of GDP produced in the oil and gas sector in 2021 was 33,930.6 million manats, which is 35.6% more than in 2017. The volume of GDP produced in the non-oil and gas sector of the economy was equal to 51,082.9 million manats in 2021, which means an increase of 26.6%

compared to the comparable period. In general, as it can be seen, compared to the oil and gas sector, the growth of the GDP produced in the non-oil and gas sector of the economy was observed at a higher rate in the oil and gas sector.

The dynamics of growth and decline of GDP and non-oil-gas GDP compared to previous years are reflected in the following graph:

Chart: GDP and non-oil-gas GDP increase (decrease), compared to the previous year, in percent

Source: State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, national accounts of Azerbaijan, statistical compilation (Baku, 2022, p. 10).

As can be seen from the graph, the highest dynamics in GDP growth was observed in 2021. In 2021, high GDP growth was observed in the non-oil sector, which was equal to 5.6 and 7.2%, respectively. Economist Igbal Mammadov believes that the development of the non-oil sector serves to make economic development dynamic and balanced. The development of the non-oil sector also plays an important role in preventing the dependence of the national economy and the state budget on oil. The development of the non-oil sector also has a direct impact on the political and economic development of the regions and the reduction of the level of poverty. The development of the non-oil sector prevents one product from taking a dominant

position in the structure of exports, and at the same time, it directly affects the neutralization of the dependence of product exports on fluctuations in the international market [7, p. 15]. In addition to agreeing with the author's opinion, we would also like to add that the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan have a fairly high economic potential in terms of the development of the non-oil sector, which essentially creates favorable conditions for the implementation of necessary measures in the direction of the development of the non-oil sector in those regions. In this regard, increasing the volume of investments in the non-oil sector of the economy is also important. In our opinion, in terms of increasing the volume of investments in the non-oil sector, the role of foreign investments should be high. First of all, this can be explained by the fact that foreign investments in the non-oil sector of the economy, in addition to being directed to the application of advanced technologies, can create favorable conditions for the implementation of competitive product production, in addition to the export of products produced in the non-oil and gas sector of the economy to foreign markets. Therefore, the attraction and stimulation of foreign investments in the non-oil and gas sector of the economy should be kept in focus. It should be taken into account that agriculture plays an important role in the structure of the non-oil and gas sector of the economy. However, it is a well-known fact that agriculture as a whole is quite dependent on natural risks, and the attraction of foreign investments should be stimulated in terms of risk insurance.

It should be taken into account that during the 44-day war in 2020, or rather, during the 2nd Karabakh war, the Republic of Azerbaijan liberated a significant part of its lands that had been occupied for up to 30 years, and from this point of view, there is enough non-oil in the liberated territories. There is potential for the development of the sector. Liberation of occupied territories for a long time promises new challenges and vectors for the economy of Azerbaijan as a whole, both geopolitically and from the point of view of globalization. So, in accordance with all these, with the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated July 7,

2021, "a new division of economic regions was formed in the Republic of Azerbaijan". According to the decree, 14 economic regions were established in our republic, which include the eastern Zangezur economic region and the Karabakh economic region, namely the territories freed from occupation. Khankendi city and Aghjabadi, Aghdam, Barda, Fuzuli, Khojaly, Khojavand, Shusha and Tartar regions are included in the Karabakh economic region, Jabrayil, Kalbajar, Gubadli, Lachin and Zangilan regions are included in the eastern Zangezur economic region[2]. Thus, it is possible to conclude in the research that there is a rich potential for the development of the non-oil sector in the field and territorial sections of the national economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Thus, in the structure of the economic potential of the territories freed from occupation, there are quite rich potentials in the field of agriculture and processing industry, as well as the production of mineral water, and the development of tourism.

One of the most important tasks in terms of economic development of the country is the development of the concept of regulating the production of food products by economic means in the territories freed from occupation, in particular, requires the implementation of appropriate credit, price, tax, investment, insurance and foreign economic policies, the formation and implementation of a system of state assistance to local commodity producers [8, p. 128-129]. In addition to agreeing with the author's views, it is also necessary to take into account that the territories freed from occupation have significant potentials in terms of the development of the non-oil sector in the territorial sections of the national economy of Azerbaijan, and the development of the processing industry in these regions, as well as the agriculture and food industry the development of integration relations between the two countries can increase the volume of competitive products produced in the field as a whole, which can create favorable conditions for reducing import dependence in the country.

As we mentioned above, a series of measures have been implemented in the direction of the development of the non-oil sector of the economy in the Republic of Azerbaijan, and in this regard, the sustainable development of the non-oil sector in

the strategic road map of the national economic perspective of the Republic of Azerbaijan, approved by the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated December 6, 2016 measures related to ensuring its development have been determined. The strategic roadmap notes that additional investment in the non-oil sector will be an important driver of a more competitive economy through 2025 and beyond. For this reason, in the future, foreign direct investments in the industrial and service sectors will be attracted on a larger scale. Investment in the non-oil sector by large foreign companies that offer technology, skills and access to global value chains will strengthen Azerbaijan's place on the global economic map. Foreign investors will be strategically attracted to Azerbaijan on 3 aspects:

- creation of extremely attractive investment opportunities (for example, industrial parks with modern infrastructure);
- targeted access to leading international companies;
- class I services for existing and future investors.

At the same time, it is mentioned in the 5th target indicators section of the strategic road map that the share of direct investments in the non-oil sector in the non-oil GDP from the current 2.67% to 4% by 2025 is an important condition. The role of foreign investors in the diversification of the economy is very important. Thus, the contribution of foreign investors is not limited to capital investment, but they also bring new skills, technologies and networking opportunities necessary to enter new sectors and value chains. It requires more investment in the non-oil sector of the economy [3, p.52-53].

As can be seen from the goals in the strategic road map, the perspective development of the non-oil sector is predicted to be developed primarily against the background of the manifestations of the post-industrial society. In other words, the diversification of the economy and at the same time the manifestations of the development of information technologies are important from the point of view of the development of the non-oil sector, and these processes imply the continuous export of products and services provided in the non-oil sector to foreign markets, which, in

fact, is the state can play an important role in ensuring the alternative of entering the budget.

As we mentioned above, there are quite diverse potential opportunities for the development of the non-oil sector in the field and territorial sections of the country's national economy. In this regard, the opportunities of the tourism sector, which is an important component of the non-oil sector, are greater.

Unfortunately, the possibilities of a number of service-oriented areas, first of all, the tourism sector, are used in our economic regions. Thus, despite the construction and commissioning of high-standard tourism enterprises in the southern, northern and western zones of the country in recent years, there is chaos. In this direction, the use of the high potential of the tourism sector and the transformation of this prospective sector of the economy - the service sector into one of the main economic sectors of our country, the creation of more new jobs and the formation of added value opportunities, and the increase of the share of the tourism sector in the structure of the economy are important conditions [6, p. 147]. In addition to agreeing with the author's views, we would like to add that there are tourism regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan with significant investment attractiveness as well as business attractiveness. Achieving noticeable progress in attracting tourism to those regions promises important prospects for our country in terms of the development of the non-oil sector.

As it is known, the tourism sector is a part of the non-oil sector, and at the same time, it is quite sensitively affected by changes in the external and internal environment as a whole. For example, the Covid-19 pandemic, which began in the spring of 2019, had a significant negative impact on the development of the tourism sector, as in all areas.

The World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) publishes forecasts of the impact of Covid-19 on the economy and different scenarios for the recovery of the tourism industry for different regions. In 2019, 330 million people worked in the tourism and travel sector. The specific weight of this sector in the global GDP is

10.3% (8.9 trillion US dollars). The share of tourism in the world export of services is about 28%. The impact of Covid-19 on the tourism and travel sector in general is characterized by job losses. Thus, global estimates of job losses range from 98.2 million to 197.5 million people. It was observed in the reduction of the specific weight in GDP. So, experts believe that this decrease is estimated from approximately 2.686 trillion to 5.543 trillion US dollars[16]. Based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, it can be concluded that the number of tourist tickets sold to foreigners and stateless persons to travel to the territory of Azerbaijan was 11,469 in 2019, 771 in 2020, and 195 in 2021. Therefore, from the analysis of statistical data, it can be concluded that the number of foreign tourists who came to Azerbaijan in 2020 decreased by 10,698 people, and by 11,274 people in 2021 compared to 2019 [4, p. 15]. The effects of Covid-19 have also had a negative impact on the amount of added value created in the mentioned field as a whole in terms of tourism development. So, if the specific weight of the added value created in the areas typical for tourism in the country's gross domestic product was 4.5% in 2019, this indicator will increase to 1.95% in 2020, and 2.2% in 2021. fell down[4, p. 19]. The Covid-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the number of employees in the enterprises engaged in the activities of travel agents and tour operators as a whole. So, if the number of employees working in the mentioned institutions was 2205 people in 2019, this indicator decreased to 1464 people in 2020 and 962 people in 2021. In other words, compared to 2019, in 2021, the number of employees in the enterprises of the tourism sector engaged only in the activities of travel agents and tour operators was reduced by 1243 people [4, p. 13].

Results and development prospects. There are quite wide economic potentials related to the development of the non-oil sector in Azerbaijan. In addition, the development of the non-oil sector plays an important role in ensuring the security of the national economy, creating added value, eliminating the dependence on oil of the state budget and the national economy as a whole, but despite all this, we can

conclude from our research that in the field of development of the non-oil sector there are also certain problems. These problems can include:

- the non-oil sector of the economy does not seem so attractive to foreign investors and business entities compared to the oil sector. This process has its own characteristics. Thus, there is a greater demand for the products produced in the oil sector, and during processing, these areas are considered to be quite modernized areas. It should be added that the oil sector of the economy, unlike the non-oil sector, is not so risky, and in this case, we mean agriculture in particular;

- there is still chaos and disorder in the development of the non-oil sector of the economy;

- compared to the oil sector, the volume of investments in the non-oil sector is significantly lower;

- noticeably low competitiveness of products and services provided in the non-oil sector of the economy;

- the low level of modernization of the non-oil sector of the economy;

- that the manifestations of the post-industrial society do not significantly penetrate the development of the non-oil sector, in other words, the non-oil sector does not use information, communication technologies and digital economic opportunities effectively;

- although a series of state programs aimed at the development of the non-oil sector have been adopted, problems are still being observed in the field of insurance, concessional conditions and crediting of this field and the application of various concessions related to the attraction of these foreign investments;

- failure to flexibly consider the experience of foreign countries in the field of developing the non-oil sector in terms of the country's natural economic characteristics.

Taking all this into account, it can be considered that the development of the non-oil sector in our country, especially in the post-oil era, is of great importance in terms of compensating the revenues from oil. Therefore, we consider it appropriate to

implement the following measures in the direction of the development of the non-oil sector:

- crediting the development of the non-oil sector on preferential terms;
- providing budget subsidies for the development of the non-oil sector;
- applying the necessary stimulating mechanisms related to the attraction of foreign investments in the development of the non-oil sector;
- creation of foreign joint ventures in the non-oil sector (agriculture, processing industry) and effective use of the unique positive aspects of this process;
- modernization of the field in order to provide competitive product production and service provision in the non-oil sector;
- copying the application of smart projects in agriculture and also in the processing industry in order to increase the role of the non-oil sector in the post-industrial society;
- increasing labor productivity in the non-oil sector and effectively using quality and non-price types of competitiveness during product production.

References:

1. Azərbaycan Respublikası regionlarının 2019-2023-cü illərdə sosial-iqtisadi inkişafı dövlət proqramı” təsdiq edilməsi haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikası prezidentinin fərmanı, 29 yanvar 2019-cu il N500
2. “Azərbaycan Respublikasında iqtisadi rayonların yeni bölgüsü haqqında” Azərbaycan Respublikası prezidentinin fərmanı, Bakı şəhəri, 7 iyul 2021-ci il
3. Azərbaycan Respublikasının milli iqtisadi perspektivi üzrə strateji yol xəritəsi, Azərbaycan Respublikası prezidentinin 2016-cı il 6 dekabr tarixli fərmanı ilə təsdiq edilmişdir, 111 s
4. Azərbaycanda turizm, statistik məcmuə, Bakı, 2022
5. Azərbaycan sənayesi, Bakı, 2002
6. E.A.Quliyev “Qarabağ və şərq Zəngəzur iqtisadi rayonlarının Azərbaycanın davamlı inkişafında rolu” , Monoqrafiya, Bakı, 2023, 320 s

7. İ.N.Məmmədov Qeyri-neft sektorunun inkişaf istiqamətləri, Bakı, 2012, 524 s
8. İ.N.Məmmədov Regionların və işğaldan azad edilmiş ərazilərin inkişaf istiqamətləri, Bakı, 2022, 240 s
9. Стрельцов Д.В. Политика Японии в сфере энергосбережения : исторические правовые аспекты // Япония 2011. Ежегодник. Москва : АИРО-XXI. 2011
10. Майкл Росс. „Добывающая Промышленность и необеспеченная часть населения” Отчет Оксфам по Америке, 2001
11. Московский Центр Карнеги при финансовой поддержке Министерства иностранных дел и по делам Содружества (Великобритания) Сравнительная история нефтезависимых экономик конца XX - начала XXI века. Исследование в рамках проекта <<Анализ исторических прецедентов и разработка рекомендаций по диверсификации ресурсной экономики>> , Москва, 2017
12. Руфат Кулиев. Интенсивное развитие экономики и “Голлодская волизна” , Dirçəliş XXI əsr, 2006 - 2007, N106-107, с 381-396
13. Терри Карл определяет страны экспортеры нефти с дефицитом капитала, такие как Мексика, Иран и Нигерия, как страны с большим населением и меньшими запасами по сравнению со странами-экспортерами с избытком капитала, такими как Саудовская Аравия и Кувейт. Терри Линн Карл. «Парадокс изобилия: нефтяной бум и нефтедобывающие государства». Издательство Калифорнийского Университета, 1997
14. Al-Shayaa M. S., Baig M. B., Straquadine G. S. Agricultural Extension in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: Difficult Present and Demanding Futures. The Journal of Animal and Plant Sciences. Vol. 22. №1. 2012
15. Reilly, J.M. (2012). Green growth and efficient use of natural resources

16. Recovery Scenarios 2020 & Economic Impact from COVID-19 Infographics. URL: <https://wttc.org/Research/Economic-Impact/Recovery-Scenarios-2020-Economic-Impact-from-COVID-19>
17. Energy Policy 34, S85-S93
18. Pearce, D., Markandya, A., & Barbier, E R. (1989)
19. The Dutch disease // The Economist. — 1977. — 26 ноября. — С. 82-83.